

Synthesis of 6-hydroxy-3-naphthylidene-5',6'-benzoflavanone

Y. B. Vibhute* and M. A. Baseer

P. G. Department of Chemistry, Yeshwant College, Nanded-431 602, India

E-mail : vibhute-y@yahoo.com

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6-Hydroxy-3-naphthylidene-5',6'-benzoflavanone has been synthesised and its acetoxy, benzoyloxy and methoxy derivatives are prepared.

3-Arylidene flavanones, also known as flavindogenide, serve as starting material for various synthetic manipulations¹ by virtue of their reactive α,β -unsaturated ketone. We have previously studied the condensation of substituted 2'-hydroxyacetophenone with naphthaldehydes in alkaline medium and obtained the respective chalcone² in good yield⁵. But when 2',5'-dihydroxyacetophenone was condensed with 1-naphthaldehyde in ethanolic KOH it afforded 6'-hydroxy-3-naphthylidene-5',6'-benzoflavanone (**1**) (Scheme 1). The structure was confirmed by converting it to the corresponding acetoxy, benzoyloxy and methoxy derivatives.

Scheme 1. Reagent : (i) 30% KOH/EtOH, 60°, 20 h.

Experimental

M.ps. were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Purity of compounds was checked by TLC on silica gel G. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 1420 spectrophotometer, PMR spectra (CDCl_3) on a Varian 200 MHz spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard and mass spectra on a VG 7070H instrument.

6-Hydroxy-3-naphthylidene-5',6'-benzoflavanone (**1**) : To a mixture of 1-naphthaldehyde (1 mmol) and 2',5'-dihydroxyacetophenone (1 mmol) dissolved in aqueous ethanol (30%; 100 ml), KOH (5 g in 5 ml H_2O) was added and kept at 60° for 20 h. The resulting orange-yellow crystals were treated with dil. HCl. The yellow solid obtained was crystallised from chloroform, (40%), m.p. 210° (Found : C, 84.09; H, 5.06. $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_3$ requires : C, 84.11; H, 4.67%); ν_{max} 3385 (OH), 1650 (C=O) and 1620 cm^{-1} (C=C); δ 3.85 (1H, s, OH), 6.75 (1H, s, H-2), 6.9–8.25 (17H, m, ArH), 8.5 (1H, s, H β); m/z 428 (M^+), 318, 291, 276, 165, 137, 83.

The 6-acetoxy, 6-benzoyloxy and 6-methoxy derivatives of **1** were prepared by following usual procedures : 6-acetoxy derivative (90%), m.p. 209° (Found : C, 81.38; H, 4.65. $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_4$ requires : C, 81.70; H, 4.66%); ν_{max} 1720, 1650, 1610 cm^{-1} ; 6-benzoyloxy derivative (85%), m.p. 162° (Found : C, 83.43; H, 4.49. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_4$ requires : C, 83.45; H, 4.50%); ν_{max} 1682, 1635, 1622 cm^{-1} ; 6-methoxy derivative (85%), m.p. 205° (Found : C, 84.15; H, 4.93. $\text{C}_{31}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_3$ requires : C, 84.16; H, 4.97%); ν_{max} 1640, 1612 cm^{-1} .

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